

Latest advances in optical networks for 5G communications and beyond

Massimo Tornatore*, Elaine Wong, Zuqing Zhu, Ramon Casellas, Balagangadhar G Bathula, Lena Wosinska

Abstract—This Special Issue contains a collection of outstanding papers covering several recent advances in optical networks for 5G communication and beyond. Papers are organized into four categories: network resource planning; optical access networks; optical fronthaul solutions; and autonomous and data-driven network management. In this introduction, a brief overview of the field is given, followed by a summary of the seventeen papers of this Special Issue, and a discussion of future directions in the field.

I. ON THE SPECIAL ISSUE

This Special Issue (SI) features latest research contributions investigating advances in optical networks enabling 5G communications and beyond. The new aggressive requirements brought on by emerging services and an increasing number of connected users and devices are shaping the evolution not only of the wireless/radio segment, but also of the higher-tier optical wired segments, spanning from access through to the backbone and core. Optical networks are already evolving from rigid infrastructures, simply designed to collect and transfer aggregated traffic, to a composite network-and-computing ecosystem, that is flexible and resource efficient thanks to the adoption of network automation, flexible grid equipment and coherent transmission.

On a longer-term research horizon, pointing towards beyond 5G (or 6G) communications, new challenging technical directions are arising that promise to revolutionize user's network experience (to name a few, multi-sensorial and holographic communication, pervasive machine learning, cell-free communication, coordination of heterogeneous wireless access technologies, and quantum communication). While this is a vision and the exact definitions of the new services have yet to be clearly identified, future service requirements are expected to be further exacerbated in terms of capacity, latency, reconfigurability, reliability and security.

Hence, simply scaling up the present mode of operation in optical networks is not an option. A redesign with new optical

Massimo Tornatore is with the Department of Electronics, Information, and Bioengineering, Politecnico di Milano, 20133 Milano, Italy, e-mail: massimo.tornatore@polimi.it.

Elaine Wong is Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, The University of Melbourne Victoria 3010, Australia, email: ewon@unimelb.edu.au.

Zuqing Zhu is with School of Science and Technology, University of Science and Technology of China Hefei 230027, China, email: zqzhu@ieee.org

Ramon Casellas is with Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/CERCA) Castelldefels, Spain, email: ramon.casellas@cttc.es.

Balagangadhar G Bathula is with Network Core & Infrastructure Services, AT&T Labs, Middletown, New Jersey, USA, email: bb4341@att.com.

Lena Wosinska is with Department of Electrical Engineering, Chalmers University of Technology 412 96 Gothenburg, Sweden, email: wosinska@chalmers.se.

*Corresponding author: M. Tornatore, massimo.tornatore@polimi.it

networks that feature in-built physical security, sub-linear bandwidth scaling costs, extreme low-latency, and reconfigurability will be needed. New, possibly disruptive, solutions in the field of optical networking and communication must be investigated, both at the data plane and at the control plane. While the impact of these 5G and beyond requirements on the wireless front-end has been the subject of intensive investigations, research addressing their impact on the optical network is still lagging behind. Hence, we believed it was appropriate to announce an IEEE JOURNAL ON SELECTED AREAS ON COMMUNICATIONS (JSAC) SI to stimulate a more thorough investigation of new research directions on optical networking and communication.

The call attracted topics ranging from pure physical-layer analysis to network optimization and automation. Some of the contributions present a clear industrial footprint, while some other papers explore more theoretical aspects, enriching the SI with a nice blend of several perspectives.

II. SUMMARY OF THE ACCEPTED ARTICLES

The seventeen accepted papers have been classified into four categories: (i) network resource planning; (ii) optical access networks; (iii) optical fronthaul solutions; and (vi) autonomous and data-driven network management.

Network Resource Planning

Several novel directions for network planning are covered in this SI. To deal with the increasing threats that natural and man-made disasters pose to optical networks, in paper “Probabilistic Shared Risk Link Groups Modeling Correlated Resource Failures Caused by Disasters” [1], authors introduce novel stochastic models to evaluate the impact of large-scale failures on optical backbones and propose an extension of the concept of shared risk link group in this context. In paper “Resource Allocation in Space Division Multiplexed Elastic Optical Networks Secured with Quantum Key Distribution” [2], authors investigate how to jointly allocate Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) channels and conventional data channels in space division multiplexed (SDM) optical networks. QKD is definitely an emerging topic, and also paper “Hybrid Trusted/Untrusted Relay Based Quantum Key Distribution over Optical Backbone Networks” [3] studies this topic, focusing on how to integrate trusted and untrusted relays in optical backbones. SDM is also investigated in “Proactive Fragmentation Management Scheme Based on Crosstalk-Avoided Batch Processing for Spectrally-Spatially Elastic Optical Networks” [4], where crosstalk considerations are leveraged during defragmentation. Finally, papers “Disruption Minimized Bandwidth Scaling in EON-enabled Transport Network Slices” [5] and “Highly-Efficient Switch

Migration for Controller Load Balancing in Elastic Optical Inter-Datacenter Networks” [6] focus on emerging network management problems in the context of slicing and controller migration in elastic optical networks.

Optical Access Networks

The access segment will have a dominant contribution in the energy consumption of future networks. Papers “Energy- and Bandwidth-Efficient, QoS-Aware Edge Caching in Fog-Enhanced Radio Access Networks” [7] and “SDN-enabled resource management for converged Fi-Wi 5G Fronthaul” [8] offer novel models and resource allocation schemes for energy minimization in next generation converged access networks. Another key challenge is related to scalable support for fronthauling of massive data flows coming from 5G and beyond antennas. In this direction, papers “Wavelength Division Multiplexed Radio over Fiber links for 5G Fronthaul Networks” [9] and “Experimental Demonstration of Extended 5G Digital Fronthaul over a Partially-Disaggregated WDM/SDM Network” [10] explore novel system architectures for optical fronthaul based on wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) and joint SDM-WDM, respectively.

Optical Fronthaul Solutions

Novel transmission technologies are being investigated to provide, as already mentioned, low-cost and scalable fronthaul solutions. In paper “Reconfigurable Fiber Wireless IFoF Fronthaul with 60 GHz Phased Array Antenna and Silicon Photonic ROADMs for 5G mmWave C-RANs” [11], authors experimentally demonstrate a bandwidth-reconfigurable mmWave Fiber Wireless (FiWi) fronthaul bus topology for 5G Centralized-Radio Access Networks (C-RAN), providing a path towards flexible and reconfigurable 5G C-RANs. In paper “Analogue Coherent-Optical Mobile Fronthaul with Integrated Photonic Beamforming” [12], authors experimentally demonstrate a mobile fronthaul methodology using analogue coherent optical transmission of native radio signals. The tunability of electro-absorption modulated lasers used as analogue coherent optical homodyne detectors, is shown to support true-time delay functionality for beam steering phased-array antennas. In paper “Quad-Mode VCSEL Optical Carrier for Long-Reach Ka-Band Millimeter-Wave Over Fiber Link” [13], authors demonstrate the establishment of a long-reach mmWave over fiber (MMWoF) link, in which one mode of the quad-mode optical carriers is modulated by 16-QAM OFDM data stream to achieve an optical single-carrier modulation.

Autonomous and Data-Driven Network Management

Network automation based on novel data-driven machine-learning solution is penetrating all network segments, and management in optical networks in particular is now subject of intense innovation. Paper “Latency-sensitive Edge/Cloud Serverless Dynamic Deployment over Telemetry-based Packet-Optical Network” [14] investigates automated deployment and reconfiguration of serverless functions in edge/cloud systems, offering an experimental demonstration of

these functions. In paper “Autonomous and Energy Efficient Lightpath Operation based on Digital Subcarrier Multiplexing” [15], authors offer several new guidelines on how to achieve autonomous operation of Digital Subcarrier Multiplexing (DSCM) systems for optical transmission. The paper “A Multi-Task-Learning-based Transfer Deep Reinforcement Learning Design for Autonomic Optical Networks” [16] proposes to use transfer learning (across different networks) for scalable and generalizable application of Deep Reinforcement Learning in the solution of routing, modulation and spectrum assignment. Extending the application to wireless optical systems, paper “Invoking Deep Learning for Joint Estimation of Indoor LiFi User Position and Orientation” [17] proposes to use artificial neural networks (ANNs) to jointly estimate the user 3D position and user equipment orientation in indoor LiFi systems.

III. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTION

Optical networks are massively-deployed and critical communication infrastructures. They form the physical backbone of today’s Internet and they are penetrating always more new domains as access and datacom. To cope with an incessant traffic increase and to comply with new emerging requirements in terms of, e.g., energy consumption and reliability, optical networks are constantly evolving, supported and stimulated by a very active industrial and academic research ecosystem.

The articles of this Special Issue provide substantial contributions in the areas of network resource planning, access and fronthaul solutions, and autonomous network management, as discussed in the previous Section. Still, research for new optical-network solutions in the context of future 5G and beyond communications is a very active and emerging area, and a variety of challenges exist which still have to be addressed, as discussed below.

A. Low-margin design and multi-band optical networks

Several core and metro optical-network deployments are currently reaching C-band spectrum saturation, and the installation/lighting-up of new fibers might be cost-prohibitive. Low-margin optical-network design and multi-band optical networks are two rising research directions in this area. Low-margin design aims at removing traditional design margin (that can be of several dB’s), by leveraging more advanced transmission techniques (as probabilistic constellation shaping), and by deriving more accurate device characterizations, typically through monitored data (e.g., elaborated using machine learning). Instead, multi-band networks exploit unconventional fiber bands (e.g., E-, S-, L-band) beyond C-band to upgrade network capacity and postpone installation of new fiber. In multi-band networks, several challenges related to both physical-layer modeling and network resource allocation still need to be addressed. Another trend that is gaining traction is the adoption of high-speed pluggable optical transceivers such as 400ZR and 800ZR, characterized by lower cost and shorter reaches compared to conventional coherent transceivers. To support these very high bit rates, research on higher baud-rate coherent optics including 128GBd, 140GBd, and 200GBd will

be needed, both in terms of device design and characterization, and in terms of network architectures and planning.

B. Physical-layer security

In light of the critical role that optical networks have in our society, new methods to enhance communication security at the optical layer have also to be investigated, and new techniques for physical-layer attack detection and mitigation need to be developed. In this context, quantum communications represent an innovative and rich research area. Quantum-based security techniques are still far from massive deployment due to multiple limitations, as low key rate, lack of telecom compatibility, and absence of proper mechanisms to maintain services running in presence of physical-layer attacks. Moreover, new optical-network solutions where quantum channels co-exist with data channel need to be devised.

C. Disaggregation and softwarization

Another trend and research direction is related to the (partial) disaggregation and softwarization of optical networks, such as the decoupling of the terminal devices (e.g., the transponders) from the rest of the line system, and the critical implications that such decoupling has in terms of control and management. In this scenario, the concept of “open networking” is attracting wide consensus. Open optical networking requires interface interoperability (typically not ensured in current deployments) and, hence, design of new hardware and software supporting this interoperability. New and/or refined architectures for open optical networks are needed, including new device and service modelling, as well as more standard and inter-operable ways to model physical impairments. Moreover, the softwarization of optical networks can leverage new technologies, such as software-defined networking (SDN), and network functions virtualization (NFV), to redefine the procedure of network control and management. Hence, optical networks can become more flexible, programmable and application-aware to enable service providers to deliver short time-to-market, elastic and cost-effective services and solutions. Finally, the importance of streaming telemetry cannot be overstated. In addition to common uses such as alarm or fault management, efficient protocols and systems are required to make use of such high volumes of data, with the ultimate goal of enabling advanced network automation. Further research is required beyond existing basic “expert systems” or more complex reinforcement learning approaches.

D. Access automation and virtualization for enterprise 5G

Another area of high interest lies in the so called “enterprise 5G”, that promises to fuel new services at higher data rates, increased network capacity and improved security indoors. In fact, ultra-high capacity indoor wireless connectivity is considered a key technology to support end-to-end delivery in the beyond-5G and 6G era. New network architectures that harness high-capacity optical fiber distribution networks along with resource sharing and interoperability between 5G and existing wireless LAN technologies such as WiFi and WiFi

6, will be key focus research areas. With this in mind, new solutions in the optical access segment will be needed, both in terms of the physical infrastructure and of the control plane. In particular, emerging services characterized by challenging latency, capacity and reliability requirements, will lead to densification of the radio access network, that, in turn, will pose several challenges for optical access networks. In terms of physical infrastructure, further densification of the fiber network and convergence of optical and wireless access networks are expected. Hence novel solution to further improve cost and energy efficiency will be an important research topic. To meet latency requirements, requests will need to be served close to users leading to a more distributed (and virtualized) cloud (“fog”) access network, where the networking and computing segments will be jointly designed. Access network automation will be the key enabler to improve user experience, operational cost and energy efficiency.

E. Data-center interconnection

The attention on enterprise 5G will also bring research interests to data-center interconnections (DCIs), because data-centers (DCs) are indispensable facilities for many 5G-based network services. The geographically-distributed DCs in a DCI can help service providers to improve their performance on service coverage, latency, and availability. Optical networking plays an important role in DCIs. With the advances on flexible-grid elastic optical networking, the conventional packet-switched architecture for DCIs might be evolved to an optical-circuit-switched one for better scalability and cost-effectiveness. Meanwhile, how to orchestrate the IT and bandwidth resources in an optical DCI to effectively support the deployment of NFV-based services is also an interesting research topic in this area.

IV. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The Guest Editors would like to thank all the authors who submitted their valuable and insightful contributions to this SI, addressing key challenges with respect to the design and management of optical networks for 5G communications and beyond, with contributions ranging from advanced system design to control architectures. The Guest Editors are indebted to Mohammed Atiquzzaman, IEEE JSAC Senior Editor, for providing advice and guidance, and to Raouf Boutaba, IEEE JSAC Editor-in-Chief, for his support and encouragement. A special thanks goes finally to Janine Bruttin, IEEE JSAC Executive Editor, for her precious help in the preparation of this SI.

Massimo Tornatore (Senior Member, IEEE) is currently an Associate Professor at Politecnico di Milano, where he received a Ph.D. degree in 2006. He also holds an appointment as Adjunct Professor at University of California, Davis, USA and as visiting a professor at the University of Waterloo, Canada. His research interests include performance evaluation and optimization of communication networks (with an emphasis on optical networking), cloud computing, and machine learning application for network management. In these areas, he co-

authored more than 400 peer-reviewed conference and journal papers (with 18 best paper awards), 2 books and 1 patent. He is a member of the Editorial Board of, among others, IEEE Communication Surveys and Tutorials, IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management and IEEE Communication Letters.

Elaine Wong (IEEE S'99-M'03-SM'14, OSA Fellow 2020) is Associate Dean and Professor at the Faculty of Engineering and Information Technology, University of Melbourne, Australia. Elaine received the BEng degree (Electrical Engineering) and Ph.D. degree from the University of Melbourne, Australia in 1997 and 2002, respectively. She has made numerous significant intellectual contributions in the field of optical fibre communications and optical networking, particularly in the areas of optical access network architectures and subsystem technologies,

energy-efficient networking and subsystem technologies, converged/hybrid fibre-wireless networks and subsystem technologies, and more recently in low-latency human-to-machine communications in the Tactile Internet and 5G and beyond networks. She was previously an Associate Editor of IEEE/OSA Journal of Optical Communications and Networking and IEEE Journal of Lightwave Technology. She is currently Secretary of the Steering Committee, IEEE Journal of Lightwave Technology, Chair of OFC 2021 Track N4: Optical Access Networks for Fixed and Mobile Services of OFC 2021 and Co-Chair of Optical Networks and Systems (ONS) Symposium of the ICC 2021.

Zuqing Zhu received his Ph.D. degree from the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of California, Davis, in 2007. From 2007 to 2011, he worked in the Service Provider Technology Group of Cisco Systems, San Jose, California, as a Software Engineer. In January 2011, he joined the University of Science and Technology of China, where he currently is a full professor. He has published more than 200 papers in peer-reviewed journals and conferences. He is an Editorial Board member of IEEE Communications Magazine, IEEE

Transactions on Network and Service Management, Optics Express, Optical Switching and Networking, and others. He has received the Best Paper Awards from IEEE ICC 2013, IEEE GLOBECOM 2013, IEEE ICNC 2014, IEEE ICC 2015, and ONDM 2018. He is a Senior Member of OSA, a Senior Member of IEEE and an IEEE Communications Society Distinguished Lecturer (2018-2019).

Ramon Casellas completed a PhD degree in Telecommunications in 2002, from the Ecole Nationale Supérieure des Télécommunications (ENST, Paris), where he worked as an Associate Professor. In March 2006, he joined the CTTC Optical Networking Area, where he currently holds a Senior Researcher position. His research interest areas include GMPLS/PCE architecture, SDN, NFV, Traffic Engineering and Distributed control schemes, with applications to Optical and Disaggregated Transport Networks. He has co-authored 5 book chapters, over

200 international and peer-reviewed journal and conference papers, 5 IETF RFCs in the TEAS, PCE and CCAMP Working Groups and several internet drafts. He is a contributor of the Open Networking Foundation (ONF) and member of the Open Disaggregated Transport Networks (ODTN) project. He has been TPC member of IPOP, IEEE SDN/NFV, Globecom, a recognized reviewer for IEEE/OSA JLT and JOCN (2014, 1015), sub-committee member or OSA OFC (N2 and N3), sub-committee member for ECOC (N6), ONDM2018 TPC chair, ONDM2020 General Chair and OFC2021 Program Chair. He is currently associate editor of the IEEE/OSA JOCN, an OSA member, an IEEE Senior Member and an IEEE ComSoc instructor on the topic of SDN for Optical Networks.

Balagangadhar G. Bathula is currently working as a Principal Member of Technical Staff, Network Core Infrastructure and Services, AT&T Labs, USA. He is leading the activities of OpenROADM Multi-Source Agreement (MSA) (disaggregated transport layer). His research interests are in software-defined networks (SDNs), Open architectures for transport, cross-layer network architectures, backbone network design, network cost optimization, optical networks & telemetry, and machine learning. He received his Ph.D. degree in electrical communication engineering

from the Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore, India. Before joining AT&T, he worked as a postdoctoral researcher in the Department of Electrical Engineering, Columbia University, New York. He served as reviewer for many IEEE/OSA conferences/journals. He has published several papers in the area of optical networks and holds 5 patents.

Lena Wosinska received her PhD degree in Photonics and Docent degree in Optical Networks from KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Sweden where she was a Full Professor of Telecommunication until October 2018. At KTH she established a world leading research group working on optical networks. Currently she is a Research Professor in Chalmers University of Technology, Sweden, where she moved together with her team. She has been working in several EU projects and coordinating a number of national and international research projects. She has

been involved in many expert assignments, including serving in the panels evaluating research project proposals for many funding agencies, guest editorships of IEEE, OSA, Elsevier and Springer journals, serving as General Chair and Co-Chair of several IEEE, OSA and SPIE conferences and workshops. She has been an Associate Editor of OSA Journal of Optical Networking and IEEE/OSA Journal of Optical Communications and Networking. Currently she is serving on the Editorial Board of Springer Photonic Networks Communication Journal and of Wiley Transactions on Emerging Telecommunications Technologies.

REFERENCES

- [1] Balázs Vass et al. “Probabilistic Shared Risk Link Groups Modeling Correlated Resource Failures Caused by Disasters”. In: *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications* (2021), pp. 1–1. DOI: 10.1109/JSAC.2021.3064652.
- [2] Elham Ehsani Moghaddam, Hamzeh Beyranvand, and Jawad A. Salehi. “Resource Allocation in Space Division Multiplexed Elastic Optical Networks Secured with Quantum Key Distribution”. In: *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications* (2021), pp. 1–1. DOI: 10.1109/JSAC.2021.3064641.
- [3] Yuan Cao et al. “Hybrid Trusted/Untrusted Relay Based Quantum Key Distribution over Optical Backbone Networks”. In: *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications* (2021), pp. 1–1. DOI: 10.1109/JSAC.2021.3064662.
- [4] Bijoy Chand Chatterjee, Abdul Wadud, and Eiji Oki. “Proactive Fragmentation Management Scheme Based on Crosstalk-Avoided Batch Processing for Spectrally-Spatially Elastic Optical Networks”. In: *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications* (2021), pp. 1–1. DOI: 10.1109/JSAC.2021.3064594.
- [5] Nashid Shahriar et al. “Disruption Minimized Bandwidth Scaling in EON-enabled Transport Network Slices”. In: *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications* (2021), pp. 1–1. DOI: 10.1109/JSAC.2021.3064643.
- [6] Yong Liu et al. “Highly-Efficient Switch Migration for Controller Load Balancing in Elastic Optical Inter-Datacenter Networks”. In: *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications* (2021), pp. 1–1. DOI: 10.1109/JSAC.2021.3064664.
- [7] Chayan Bhar and Erik Agrell. “Energy-and Bandwidth-Efficient, QoS-Aware Edge Caching in Fog-Enhanced Radio Access Networks”. In: *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications* (2021), pp. 1–1. DOI: 10.1109/JSAC.2021.3064659.
- [8] E. Datsika et al. “SDN-enabled resource management for converged Fi-Wi 5G Fronthaul”. In: *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications* (2021), pp. 1–1. DOI: 10.1109/JSAC.2021.3064651.
- [9] Gaurav Pandey, Amol Choudhary, and Abhishek Dixit. “Wavelength Division Multiplexed Radio over Fiber links for 5G Fronthaul Networks”. In: *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications* (2021), pp. 1–1. DOI: 10.1109/JSAC.2021.3064654.
- [10] J. M. Fabrega et al. “Experimental Demonstration of Extended 5G Digital Fronthaul over a Partially-Disaggregated WDM/SDM Network”. In: *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications* (2021), pp. 1–1. DOI: 10.1109/JSAC.2021.3064645.
- [11] Apostolos Tsakyridis et al. “Reconfigurable Fiber Wireless IFOF Fronthaul with 60 GHz Phased Array Antenna and Silicon Photonic ROADMs for 5G mmWave C-RANs”. In: *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications* (2021), pp. 1–1. DOI: 10.1109/JSAC.2021.3064649.
- [12] Dinka Milovancev et al. “Analogue Coherent-Optical Mobile Fronthaul with Integrated Photonic Beamforming”. In: *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications* (2021), pp. 1–1. DOI: 10.1109/JSAC.2021.3064640.
- [13] Cheng-Ting Tsai et al. “Quad-Mode VCSEL Optical Carrier for Long-Reach Ka-Band Millimeter-Wave Over Fiber Link”. In: *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications* (2021), pp. 1–1. DOI: 10.1109/JSAC.2021.3064644.
- [14] István Pelle et al. “Latency-sensitive Edge/Cloud Serverless Dynamic Deployment over Telemetry-based Packet-Optical Network”. In: *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications* (2021), pp. 1–1. DOI: 10.1109/JSAC.2021.3064655.
- [15] Luis Velasco et al. “Autonomous and Energy Efficient Lightpath Operation based on Digital Subcarrier Multiplexing”. In: *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications* (2021), pp. 1–1. DOI: 10.1109/JSAC.2021.3064698.
- [16] Xiaoliang Chen et al. “A Multi-Task-Learning-based Transfer Deep Reinforcement Learning Design for Autonomic Optical Networks”. In: *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications* (2021), pp. 1–1. DOI: 10.1109/JSAC.2021.3064657.
- [17] Mohamed Amine Arfaoui et al. “Invoking Deep Learning for Joint Estimation of Indoor LiFi User Position and Orientation”. In: *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications* (2021), pp. 1–1. DOI: 10.1109/JSAC.2021.3064637.